

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE "FLIPPED CLASSROOM" TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AT SENIOR GRADES OF A SECONDARY SCHOOL

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Annotation: The goal of this article is to present a review of recent research on the implementation of the "flipped classroom" approach in education. The benefits of this model for both students and teachers will be highlighted before discussing the contributions of the flipped classroom to teaching. Further, a section outlining the information gap in the literature will discuss the need for future study. In conclusion, this article makes an argument for the flipped classroom's value in education and offers suggestions on how to modify it to better suit teaching and learning activities. This article examines the features of using the innovative technology "flipped lesson" when teaching a foreign language in senior grades of school. The search for new technologies for learning is due to the growing role of self-education in the concept of general cultural competencies of a modern specialist. Therefore, modern pedagogical technologies help to develop the skills of independent learning in schoolchildren. The advantages of the studied technology are found in increasing the time for individual independent work with schoolchildren, in the ability to give additional general cultural knowledge in parallel with the study of a certain thematic section, on the one hand, and also in the inclusion of schoolchildren in active cognitive activity, the development of their independence, on the other hand.

Key words: flipped classroom, blended lesson, student-centered lesson, independent learning, innovative technology.

Аннотация: Цель этой статьи — представить обзор недавних исследований по реализации подхода «перевернутый класс» в образовании. Преимущества этой модели как для учащихся, так и для учителей будут подчеркнуты перед обсуждением вклада перевернутого класса в преподавание. Кроме того, в разделе, посвященном информационному пробелу в литературе, будет обсуждаться необходимость будущих исследований. В заключение в этой статье приводится аргумент в пользу ценности перевернутого класса в образовании и предлагаются предложения о том, как изменить его, чтобы он лучше подходил для преподавания и обучения. В данной статье рассматриваются особенности использования инновационной технологии «перевернутый урок» при обучении иностранному языку в старших классах школы. Поиск новых технологий обучения обусловлен возрастающей ролью самообразования в концепции общекультурных компетенций современного специалиста. Поэтому современные педагогические технологии помогают формировать у школьников навыки самостоятельного обучения. Преимущества изучаемой технологии заключаются в увеличении времени на индивидуальную самостоятельную работу со школьниками, в возможности дать дополнительные общекультурные знания параллельно с изучением определенного тематического раздела, с одной стороны, а

также во включении школьников в активной познавательной деятельности, развитие их самостоятельности, с другой стороны.

Ключевые слова: перевернутый урок, смешанный урок, урок направленный на ученика, самостоятельное обучение, инновационные технологии.

Introduction

The policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is focused on the implementation of the task of improving the quality of education as well as achieving the goal of training competent and competitive specialists. The main thing is to find other approaches in the education system. First of all, such issues of modernization of independent learning and the ability to acquire knowledge as one of the key general cultural competencies are brought out. As part of this aspiration, in recent years there has been a change in the curricula of secondary schools in the amount of hours for independent work and the study of foreign languages, in particular English and the introduction of a second foreign language. The primary task of these changes is the problem of accustoming students to work independently. How to teach to think? How to force to study and read? How to give motivation to continuously self-study? Many scientists and educators deal with such issues, and this task is relevant not only in our country, but throughout the world. Today's modern teachers find and solve these problems by modernizing the innovative technologies used and introduced into school practice. The search for new methods in the case of a school worker is associated with the use of modern technology for working with educational and scientific information (computers, the Internet, multimedia and audio, video equipment, with open access to MOOCs) and the obligation to actively and expediently use it in the classroom. It is necessary to know and understand that the appearance of innovative pedagogical technologies in school educational practice changes its organizational, pedagogical, psychological and didactic content, and changes in the educational form are required. The current didactic systems in school education, as a rule, are still based on the translational teaching form. The main role in this didactic system is given to the teacher. The learner acts as a passive recipient of knowledge.

Internet-based technologies are becoming more popular in the sphere of education. When educational institutions use intranets, websites, and computer-mediated communication, electronic learning environments and online courses are created [21, p. 263-272]. Blended learning is a method of learning that integrates various learning technologies with in-person classroom instruction, such as o

nline courses, real-time collaborative software, and electronic performance support systems [19, p. 51-54]. A learning strategy known as the "flipped classroom" occasionally contributes significantly to blended learning [1, p.227-236].

The use of the innovative technology "inverted lesson" (inverted lesson) together with collective learning in cooperation allows the teacher to increase the effective result of the educational process due to the fact that it saves time, which goes in favor of independent work with each student. As well as increasing the share of personal responsibility of each student for the result of training. The Flipped Class technology was borrowed from American teachers D. Bergman and A. Sams [5]. Being at first by filling gaps in the knowledge of students due to absence from the lessons, it is introduced into the teaching methodology, the essence of which reflects its name. The classic concept of a flipped classroom, according to Bergmann Overmyer & Wilie [4], involves substituting videos for direct instruction and enticing students to concentrate on significant learning activities with their teachers inside the classroom.

According to the argument, the flipped classroom is misunderstood, and this misunderstanding can be rectified by defining the flipped classroom as individualized instruction where students take ownership of their own learning. The teacher can act as a facilitator as well as boost interaction and one-on-one time with pupils while using the flipped classroom method. Another way to describe the flipped classroom is to develop problem-based learning within the classroom and substitute instructional videos for direct instruction in order to give students access to educational material whenever and wherever they need it [2];[11]. According to Hamdan et al. [9], screencasting computer work while narrating it, filming teachers as they teach, or compiling video lessons from reputable websites are all effective ways to offer training.

Methodology

The traditional classroom-lesson system, the new technology "Flipped Lesson" turns/reverses the learning process. New material taught at the lesson by the teacher is studied at home by the student independently. That is, acquaintance with new material takes place at home, and in the classroom, together with the group, it is practiced with the participation of a teacher. An important feature of the "flipped lesson", in contrast to the traditional lesson, is "the transfer of the process of cognition, learning to independent work outside the lesson, which helps save time in the lesson and help deepen knowledge and understanding of the material directly in class".

The main plot of the "flipped lesson" technology is a video or presentation with which the student must work independently at home. A video lecture can often be viewed and revisited by a student as key material. Such lessons are created and sent by the teacher on the Internet, or stored in some kind of online file sharing. In this work, we chose the application "Telegram" "Formative" and "Padlet". In Telegram, a chat is created with a specific group and links to video tutorials, presentations and tasks on the topic are posted there. After viewing and reading, the student can ask questions on the topic for general discussion.

People have different learning styles, and personality type plays a big part in determining how a person learns best, according to Borg and Shapiro [6, p.3-25]. Learning may be hindered and interest in the subject matter may decline if an instructor's teaching style and a learner's learning style are incompatible. According to Lage, Platt, and Treglia [12, p.30], the use of new learning technologies makes it possible to move lectures that are typically held inside the classroom outside the classroom and learning activities that take place outside the classroom inside the classroom under the direction of the instructor. In the pedagogical strategy known as "flipped teaching," homework assignments and classroom activities are switched around [20]. A review of the literature reveals that there are synonymous terms with flipped teaching which have been used in different studies [12, p.81-96]. The term 'inverted classroom' is used by Lage and Platt [13, p. 30], 'just-in-time teaching' is used by Novak [17, p.63-73], 'flipped classroom' is used by Bergmann and Sams [3, p.25-25] and 'inverted learning' is used by Barker, Quennerstedt & Annerstedt [2, p.18] in order to explain the same approach. An effective flipped classroom needs to have both planning and responsibility. The usage of a flipped classroom format can stop content from spreading and enhance student execution of learnt activities. Moreover, it is possible to complete all Bloom's Taxonomy levels. Inside-classroom content fits in the higher order levels of Bloom's Taxonomy, such as generating, evaluating, analyzing, and applying, whereas content from outside the classroom fits in the lower levels, such as comprehending and remembering [18, p.585-588].

The potential effects of flipping the classroom on the academic performance, learning attitudes, and involvement levels of English language learners were investigated in Hung work [10]. It was discovered that the structured and semi-structured flipped lessons were more successful than the non-flipped lessons after using three different flipped teaching formats.

R. Slavin in 1986 researched and developed a form of this method "Jigsaw-2". In this form, he considered the work of students in groups of 4-5 people. Each student receives the same material. The team, having carefully studied the topic, becomes an expert in it. Then meetings of experts from different groups are organized. In the final cycle, all students undergo an individual survey, in which the result is revealed, and the results are summarized for evaluation. The team that managed to score the highest amount of points is encouraged.

With such work, the grouping takes place taking into account the individual and psychological characteristics of each member. When performing a common task, students independently determine the roles of each member. Team members themselves monitor the correctness of the tasks performed by partners. They themselves conduct a rating of the activity of each member of the group in solving a common problem.

As a result, from the very beginning, teams are given two tasks: 1) academic - to achieve some kind of cognitive goal; 2) socio-psychological - to show in the course of the assignment a certain culture of communication. The teacher must analyze not only the success of the educational task, but also the nature of their communication, and also the way they provide mutual assistance to each other. Such a collaborative learning system is not only student-student cooperation, but also student-teacher cooperation. Therefore, in such work, it is necessary to involve students in the planning of the curriculum of the course. This is permissible "in the presence of a variable component of the content of education, which is filled with personal meaning". To introduce a variable component into the content of the course being studied, it is considered the best form of presentation of any topic - block. In the process of learning, individual blocks can be replaced and replenished. The content of each training block may include: 1) a topic that may contain material grouped around fundamental educational objects, which consists of: a) the main part of the compulsory study; b) a variable given part, that is, materials of the student's choice; c) a variable current part where the texts are selected by the students themselves; 2) exercises and buildings for students on compiling a portfolio on the subject Issues with the creation of individual variable components are largely solved through the use of numerous video lessons that already exist. Materials among domestic platforms containing educational video materials such as (<https://online.uzedu.uz/>, <https://onlinedars.uz/course/all?free=1>), from foreign platforms (<http://uchportal.ru>), video lessons on subjects (<https://interneturok.ru/>) (<http://virtualacademy.ru/videouroki>), (<https://www.khanacademy.org/>) [16-18]. and others. Here, not only video materials, but also presentations, text forms with tasks, online textbooks and others can be a source for self-preparation.

Next, it is considered that effective result can be achieved by using the "flipped classroom" technology in English classes at senior grades of school, where 4 hours a week are allotted for classroom work. This technology helps to change the types of activities in the classroom in the direction of increasing the interest and activity of students studying a non-native language. Thus, the teacher frees up time for himself, which was previously allotted for explaining a new topic. This time is converted into a preliminary preparatory block. However, in the classroom

there is an opportunity not only to check the general understanding of the topic, for example, through a quick survey of the basic rules related to it. The teacher, using this, can pay extra attention to examples of exceptions and irregular forms. When a student independently studies new material, the teacher must take out new unfamiliar vocabulary for preliminary independent study. For example, by inviting students to select it from a series of short video clips on a new topic. But for listening assignments, careful preliminary preparation is necessary. In such work, a wide range of tasks may include:

- study of a video fragment similar in subject matter to the audio text intended for listening;
- analysis of a silent video sequence, with voice acting, which is the next audio text to be listened to;
- try to describe the silent video in your own words;
- analysis and implementation with the vocabulary selected by the teacher from the audio text, including its translation;
- compiling phrases and sentences, grouping by topic, etc.

The "flipped lesson" technology needs to be looked at more broadly, then it can be used to solve not only internal problems related to improving foreign language learning in the context of the development of students' independence. But more global issues in education related to teaching a foreign language are, first of all, the problem of the internationalization of education. In our opinion, this problem can be solved within the framework of the English language discipline using the "flipped lesson" technology. Let's give an example: one of the elements of the content of the English language program is the topic "Education", which includes such subsections as: secondary education in Uzbekistan and abroad; the school where I study; My school life; My schedule. There are questions of academic mobility, student international relations, competitions, grants, scholarships for students in Uzbekistan. The selection of this topical topic is expedient for filling the content of the topic "Education". When implementing the "flipped lesson" technology, we offer students to independently familiarize themselves with the presentations of European and world organizations on the Internet. Organizations that deal with issues of grant support and educational mobility of students.

One of the options for learning in collaboration is called "Puzzle" ("jigsaw"), developed by Professor Elliot Aronson in 1978 [29]. With the "Puzzle" groups of 6 people are formed to work on the studied material. The teacher breaks the material into logical or semantic parts. Let's consider in an example, in the topic "Traditions of Great Britain" for an English lesson, we can highlight sights, holidays, sports, etc. A group member is looking for material in his/her part. Then, students studying the same issue, but in different teams, meet and exchange the found material as experts on this issue ("meeting of experts"). "Experts" returning to their team teach what they learned to other members of the group. The rest, in turn, talk about their part of the task. The main thing is to master the material of all parts. So you need to carefully listen to teammates and take notes. In this case, no additional effort is required from the teacher. Group members are interested in their partners honestly fulfilling their assigned task, because this may affect the assessment. In the final stage, the teacher can ask any member of the team to answer any question on the topic studied. Most importantly, all members must answer the questions posed by the teacher.

Such innovative technology "inverted lesson" will be energy-intensive, interesting and fruitful for everyone. Such technology will require significant and creative work. Thus, the "flipped lesson" method will create an additional burden on the teacher and student. The use of such

technology also implies the solution of a number of interrelated issues: a) in the educational process, a change in the relationship between the student and the teacher; b) in the process of work, ensuring a dialogue not only between the teacher and students, but also between students; c) an effective correlation of the found methods and technologies with the “flipped lesson” technology.

Results

Abovementioned shows that the new pedagogical technology “flipped lesson” when learning a foreign language shows a wide range of opportunities that are directly related to teaching a foreign language. At the same time, the teacher has time to work individually with the student. There is an opportunity to receive additional general cultural knowledge in parallel with the study of a certain thematic section. Such work allows solving important general educational problems such as:

- activation of the student's cognitive activity;
- manifestation of independence of work of students.

We consider such a process of work to be promising in terms of introducing into the practice of teaching a foreign language in high school. The practical application of the innovative methodology “flipped lesson” requires the teacher not only to be open to innovation, but also to have pedagogical skills. To do this, we need to review work programs and learning objectives. Convert theoretical material into electronic format. Think over and create a new system of testing and assessment of knowledge. The main thing in this work is to prepare creative and practical tasks for the joint work of students and the teacher within the lesson.

The advantages and disadvantages of this innovative technology are given in great detail in the works of many researchers such as O.F. Bryksina [22, p.53–57], E.V. Vulfovich [23, p.88–95], E.V. Zvereva [24, p.446–456], O.S. Kvashnina [25, p.108–112], S. G. Litvinova [26, p. 233–247], N. V. Litonina [27, p.49–52], A. V. Loginova [28, 114–111], H. Marshall [15], J. Graney [8], K. A. Muldrow [16], etc.

The advantages include:

- Giving pupils a chance to gather background knowledge prior to the class activity,
- Encouraging students to attend lectures online and prepare for class activities beforehand,
- Planning assessment techniques,
- Making connections between in-class and extracurricular activities,
- Providing direction that is concisely worded and arranged,
- Giving students enough time to complete their assignments,
- Encouraging learners to become a community of learners,
- Giving prompt feedback on group or individual projects,
- Enabling students to use well-known technologies that are simple for them to access.
- free time for independent work in class;
- individual approach to each student;
- the removal of the role of the teacher in the direction of the tutor, coordinator, mentor, students' actions, which create conditions for the development of their independence. And also to include them in an active, independent and cognitive activity;
- a chance for a student to study theoretical material independently at a convenient time. He may return to it several times.

According to Enfield [7, p.14-27], the flipped classroom method encourages students to learn outside of the traditional classroom setting. Students can select and employ the most effective

study technique while following the lesson at their own pace. Hung [10] provided evidence that this instructional technique has a beneficial impact on students' engagement, satisfaction, and performance. According to McLaughlin and Rhoney [14, p.12-19], teachers who employed the flipped classroom model were more aware of effective teaching methods. Also, according to Kong [11, p.160-173], employing the flipped classroom paradigm helps teachers have better tools, participate in reflective dialogues, and share their instructional practices.

A visible disadvantage is the lack of a guarantee that all students will study the material and come prepared, on which the activity of the group and, therefore, cooperation will depend as it is difficult to control.

Thus, the functions, analysis and rethinking of the content and organization of learning when using the "flipped lesson" will become the starting point for activating students' independent work. This will become possible:

- 1) when studying in cooperation;
- 2) with the individualization of the process of mastering knowledge;
- 3) with the formation of the creative potential of students;
- 4) with the development of cognitive interests of students;
- 5) with the introduction of variable learning content.

Conclusion

Although it can be challenging to accommodate each individual student's learning style in a typical classroom, the flipped classroom pedagogical approach offers instruction that takes into account students' different learning preferences. In-class learning activities can now be conducted outside of the classroom, and out-of-class activities can now be conducted in the classroom under the guidance of the instructor. With the help of videos that students may access at any time, anywhere, the flipped classroom lets teachers substitute one-on-one education with problem-based learning during face-to-face teaching.

The literature review reveals that the adoption of flipped classrooms makes a greater contribution to the educational environment. First off, using the flipped classroom paradigm allows for the completion of all levels of Bloom's Taxonomy as well as student applications regarding learnt topics. Students are encouraged to leave the classroom to learn independently of time and place and to select the most effective study technique for their own learning needs. Also, it was discovered that teachers who employed the flipped classroom approach had better resources, participated in reflective dialogues, and shared their instructional strategies with one another.

In order to increase engagement and individualized contact time between students and instructors in the classroom, it was discovered that the flipped classroom approach has been used in a variety of educational fields. For a brief time, many courses, including clinical pharmacy practice, nutrition, neurologic pharmacotherapy, microeconomics, population health, chemistry, actuarial science, English language, and linear algebra, have switched the in-class and out-of-class activities. The vast majority of research demonstrate that attitudes about the flipped classroom strategy significantly improved.

The findings of this study's literature review show that there is a knowledge gap regarding the flipped classroom strategy. It is advised to conduct further research on the use of technology and superior assessment tools, as well as on the design requirements for flipped classrooms. Also, research on the impact of flipped learning environments on achieving learning outcomes

and the ideal proportion of face-to-face training that maximizes learning benefits for students is advised.

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